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Experimental Effect of Liquid Sloshing on the Dynamic Behaviour of Flared Folding Wingtips

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A wind tunnel experiment is presented that studies the static and dynamic aeroelastic behaviour of a “floating wingtip fuel tank”. This device consists of a ‘freely floating’ wingtip with an additional mass attached, in the form of a liquid-filled fuel tank, to ensure an optimal lift distribution during cruise, whilst also potentially acting as a passive load alleviation device. The static aeroelastic results show that by altering the fuel tank filling level, the wingtip can float at an optimal angle for aerodynamic efficiency across a range of angles of attack. Furthermore, by altering the position of the fuel tank it is shown that the maximum fuel load can be increased whilst maintaining the optimal equilibrium angle of the wingtip. Regarding gust load alleviation, it is shown that with careful selection of the centre of mass of the wingtip, load alleviation can be achieved that is comparable to that of a wingtip without a fuel tank. Furthermore, the effect of fluid motion is shown to have a negligible effect on the response to one-minus-cosine encounters. However, reductions of up to 10% in RMS root bending moment are seen during random turbulence encounters. Such results are also confirmed by a numerical model incorporating a simple reduced order ‘fluid sloshing’ model. Overall, the floating wingtip fuel tank is shown to be a viable concept, which could enable longer wingspans whilst increasing the fuel capacity of an aircraft.

I. Introduction

To drive the development of the next generation of green aircraft, schemes such as the Carbon Offsetting and Reduction Scheme for International Aviation (CORSIA)[1], aim to place a cost on emissions, incentivising the industry to improve overall aircraft efficiency through the use of radical design solutions. Many such solutions aim to improve efficiency by increasing the wingspan and therefore aspect ratio of future aircraft. Calderon et al. [2] showed through a conceptual design study that, even when weight is considered, the optimal wingspan is much larger than that used by current designs. However, increasing the span of the next generation of aircraft also affects ground operations, with current infrastructure at many airports - such as gate, runway and taxiway separation - only capable of servicing aircraft up to a specific wingspan [3, 4].

With the aim of enabling larger wingspans, there has recently been considerable research into the Folding Wingtip (FWT) concept. This device allows the span of an aircraft to be reduced on the ground by folding the wingtips up on landing - allowing aircraft to still operate using current airport infrastructure whilst also having a larger span during flight, reducing induced drag. The most notable recent example is the Boeing 777X, allowing the aircraft to fit into the same 65m gate as its predecessor, whilst also being able to increase its wingspan in flight by 7 metres [5]. Whilst the wingtips of the 777X can only be operated on the ground, the inclusion of such a mechanism raises the question as to whether folding wingtips can be utilised in-flight for aerodynamic or structural benefits.

One such device is the Flared Folding Wingtip (FFWT) [6–17]. As shown in Fig. 1, this device consists of a FWT in which the hinge line is rotated so that it is no longer parallel with the oncoming flow, with the magnitude of this rotation being defined as the flare angle, Λ . In this configuration, an increase in the fold angle, θ , produces a decrease in the local Angle of Attack (AoA), and vice versa in the other direction. Therefore, when a FFWT is free to rotate, the fold angle tends to an equilibrium position, defined as the coast angle, about which the aerodynamic and gravitational moments balance, and the system is statically stable.

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Fig. 1 Representation of the flared folding wingtip concept, with a flare angle, Λ , of 20 deg, at 0 and 45 deg fold angle θ .

In-flight the primary purpose of an FFWT is as a passive gust alleviation device [6–11], where the large spanwise moment arm of a wingtip means it has a significant impact on the bending stress seen along the entire wingspan. Although, more recent research has focused on quantifying the effect of FFWTs on the handling qualities [13, 18] and roll performance [14] of an aircraft.

When an FFWT is free to rotate, the wingtip produces enough lift to balance its own weight, which is generally less than this section of the wing would generate if it were locked at a fold angle of zero degrees. This reduction of lift on the wingtip significantly reduces the overall aerodynamic efficiency of the aircraft. Therefore, concepts looking to utilise this technology, such as Airbus’s upcoming *extra high-performance wing demonstrator**, aim to use a so-called Semi-Aeroelastic Hinge (SAH)[19–21]. This device allows the FFWT to be in either: a “fixed state” where the wingtip is rigidly connected to the inner wing via an actuator (allowing the fold angle of the wingtips to be manually adjusted), or a “free state” in which the wingtips are free to rotate about the hinges. Therefore, the wingtip could be locked in flight for optimal cruise performance, whilst unlocked during manoeuvres and gust encounters to alter the dynamic behaviour and reduce peak wing loading.

An alternative concept to the SAH is to adjust the mass distribution of an FFWT so that in cruise the wingtip generates the required amount of lift to float at the angle which optimises the aerodynamic efficiency of the aircraft. Such a device would be a truly passive form of gust load alleviation when compared to the SAH, as it would not require the hinge to be released when, for example, a gust encounter is detected. For this paper, it is envisaged that fuel could be utilised as this additional mass, which would both provide an operational benefit by increasing the range of the aircraft, whilst also providing a mechanism to tailor the total mass of the wingtip during flight.

Such a concept is not actually new; in the 1960s a “Floating Wing Fuel Tank” was tested to increase the range of military helicopters [22]. It consisted of a wing with multiple fuel tank sections, connected to the fuselage through a hinge at an angle of 45 degrees, and was designed to reduce the bending loads transmitted to the fuselage when compared to a fixed wing. Additionally, Project Long-Tom, in the 1950s, attached two freely floating fuel tanks to the wingtips of a Beechcraft L-23, which tripled the range of the aircraft with only minor reductions in its basic performance [23]. However, testing into such devices was never continued, likely due to the development of in-air-refuelling.

For the purposes of dynamic analysis, such as during gust excitations or manoeuvres, the liquid stored within a wing cannot be assumed as a solid mass, as fuel sloshing effects will alter the dynamic behaviour of the system, particularly when large displacements, such as those seen on an FFWT [8] are considered. Investigations into fuel sloshing effects in wing configurations have often considered the effect on flutter response in aeroelastic frameworks. In the Mid 20th century, Widmayer and Reese [24, 25] explored these effects experimentally on external pylon-mounted fuel tanks, noting a reduction in the flutter amplitude and speed with the inclusion of sloshing behaviour, with Sewall [26] extending this work experimentally for the case of internally stored fuel. More recently, such effects have often been explored numerically at varying fidelities, such as a linearised added-mass fuel model coupled with a doublet-lattice aerodynamics [27]; modelling the fuel as a spring-mass-damper system coupled with unsteady strip theory [28]; or a multi-physics aeroelastic analysis, utilising inviscid aerodynamic Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) coupled to a

*<https://www.airbus.com/en/newsroom/press-releases/2021-09-airbus-launches-extra-high-performance-wing-demonstrator-to-fortify> [retrieved 01/06/2022]

Fig. 2 An overview of the wind tunnel model including the location of key instrumentation

Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) based sloshing model [29].

Studies investigating the effect of fuel slosh on factors other than flutter have also been considered. Classically, Smith and Charles [30] performed a wind-tunnel analysis of a scaled aircraft carrying spherical fuel tanks, evaluating the influences on lateral stability. Luskin and Ellis [31] used a simplified spring-mass-damper model for fuel slosh to analytically evaluate the influence on aircraft buffeting and flight dynamics. More recently, numerical approaches using CFD or reduced order models have become popular for novel analysis of aircraft sloshing problems. Pizzoli [32] used a reduced-order sloshing model (ROM) integrated with a flexible aircraft to explore aeroelastic and stability response. This ROM was extended by Saltari et al. [33] using volume of fluid CFD results to train and validate reduced order models, for integration into aerospace design. De Courcy et al. [34] use a simplified equivalent mechanical model (EMM) to assess the load alleviation capabilities of sloshing fuel during atmospheric gusts in an aeroelastic setting. Later used in the work of Saltari et al. [35] and combined with other reduced-order-models, highlighting the requirement for complex hydrodynamics models to suitably capture liquid damping following gust excitation and during limit-cycle oscillations. A careful balance is required when including sloshing models in coupled frameworks, simple EMMs can provide rapid solution capabilities but are valid only in regimes of small deformations and linear fluid response, whereas high-fidelity CFD models can capture three-dimensional highly nonlinear fluid response but demand large execution times. Therefore, within this work, a sloshing ROM previously coupled to nonlinear structural [36] and aeroelastic [35] models is employed, designed specifically to capture fluid response under small and large excitation conditions in an in-expensive framework.

This paper will experimentally explore the effect of liquid sloshing on the static and dynamic behaviour of a wind tunnel model incorporating FFWTs with externally mounted tanks, which were capable of holding either liquid or a solid mass analogue. This model will be used to investigate the static behaviour of such a concept across a range of flight speeds and AoAs, focusing on how the optimal wingtip mass varies to achieve the best aerodynamic efficiency. Secondly, the model is used to assess the effect of such a device on the loads experienced by an aircraft during one-minus-cosine gust encounters and random turbulence. Finally, the numerical model is used to assess its capabilities in capturing the highly nonlinear fluid response excited by the FFWT by comparing key results, in turn using it to explore the mechanisms driving the behaviour witnessed in the wind tunnel.

II. Description of Experimental Setup

The primary aim of this investigation was to assess how adding mass to an FFWT, via an external tank, affects both its static performance, and dynamic behaviour during gust encounters. To achieve this a wind tunnel model was developed comprising of the same fuselage as detailed in [18], with a new, straight, rectangular wing incorporating two FFWTs, as shown in Figs. 2 & 3. The wing had a span of 1.32 m, a constant chord of 0.11 m, zero degrees spanwise twist, and a constant aerofoil section chosen from the ARA-D series, with a maximum thickness of 16% of the chord [37]. This aerofoil section was chosen due to its relatively linear lift-curve-slope and benign variation in pitching moment with AoA, when compared to other cambered aerofoils of a similar thickness.

The design of the wing included a central spar, made of type 304 stainless steel, which spanned the majority of the inner wing, as shown in Fig. 3. The thickness and width of the central spar were 4 mm and 18 mm respectively, and was

Fig. 3 A diagram illustrating the construction of each wing and also indicating the three possible locations in which the external tanks could be mounted (points 1, 2 and 3).

Fig. 4 The front and side cross-sections of the external tank, highlighting the three key dimensions which define the internal geometry

sized to give good separation between the first wing bending and wingtip flapping modes, ensuring the flutter speed of the model was outside the intended testing envelope.

Three, 3D-printed, wing sections could be slid over and affixed to the central spar. These sections contacted the spar in one location and there was a 1 mm gap between each section, meaning they did not contribute to the stiffness of the wing structure. The construction of the wingtip hinge was metallic and featured a removable locking pin which meant the wingtip could be in either a ‘Free’ configuration in which the wingtip was free to rotate, or a ‘Locked’ configuration, in which the fold angle of the wingtip was locked at zero degrees. To maximise the effect of liquid sloshing within the external tanks a relatively low flare angle[†] of 10 degrees was chosen in an attempt to maximise the motion of the liquid.

As shown in Fig. 3, the external tank could be mounted to the wingtip in one of three locations. Its cross-section was cylindrical with a spherical cap at each end. Additionally, the tank had a flat top to ensure there was enough material thickness to attach it to the wingtip. Figure 4 shows that the geometry of this tank could be defined by three parameters: its radius r , length L , and the height of the flat top relative to the centre of the cylinder, h . The volume of the tank is defined by

$$V = 2\frac{2}{3}\pi r^3 + \pi r^2(L - 2r) - \frac{1}{3}(r - h)^2(2r + h) - \left(r^2 \arccos \frac{h}{r} - \sqrt{2rh - h^2}\right) \quad (1)$$

where the first term represents the spherical caps, the second the central cylinder, the third the section of the caps within the flat section and the fourth the volume of the cylinder within the flat section. h , L and r were chosen as 16 mm, 160 mm and 22 mm respectively, leading to a tank volume of 195 ml.

Given the relatively small volume of the tanks used in this experiment, surface tension can have a noticeable influence on the sloshing dynamics [38], potentially altering the initial free-surface disturbance and subsequent dynamics. To mitigate this, an aqueous solution of isopropanol at a concentration of 20% was used in these experiments. Such a solution has a surface tension of 30.6 Nm^{-1} [39], which is 42% that of distilled water. The density of this solution is 0.96 gcm^{-3} , leading to the percentage filling levels shown in Tab. 1 for each configuration.

In addition to the external tank capable of holding liquid, an additional tank was designed which had the same external geometry, but in which up to six 25 g masses could be replaced, as shown in Fig. 5. By testing both the liquid and solid tank with the same total mass, the effect of the liquid on the motion of the wing could be isolated. In total seven discrete filling cases could be tested, which are summarised in Tab. 1. Due to the small difference in the empty mass of the liquid and solid tanks, slightly more liquid was needed in each case to achieve the same total mass.

Regarding instrumentation, the model was also equipped with an RLS RM08[‡] encoder in both hinges, allowing fold angles to be measured. Additionally, a half Wheatstone bridge was bonded at the root of each wing in such a configuration as to measure the wing root bending moment. All of the instrumentation was connected to a selection of National Instruments PXI cards[§] hosted within a National Instruments PXIe-1082 chassis, with the MATLAB Data Acquisition API being utilised to sample the sensors at a rate of 200Hz.

[†] the angle between the centre-line of the model and the hinge line

[‡] <https://www.rls.si/eng/rm08-super-small-non-contact-rotary-encoder> [retrieved 2 December 2022]

[§] <https://www.ni.com/en-gb/shop/pxi.html> [retrieved 2 December 2022]

Fig. 5 A picture of the solid external tank with the lid removed, revealing the six possible locations at which a 25 g mass could be attached.

Fig. 6 An overview of the wind tunnel model taken upstream of the model, which indicates the location of the gust vanes

Table 1 The required liquid mass, and associated percentage filling level, to achieve the same total mass as the solid tank, for each mass case.

Mass Case [g]	Liquid Mass [g]	Filling Level [%]
0.0	11.7	6
25.0	36.7	19
50.0	61.7	32
75.0	86.7	45
100.0	111.7	58
125.0	136.7	71
150.0	161.7	84

Fig. 7 A key describing the naming convention for configurations including an external fuel tank

Fig. 8 The vertical velocity component experienced by the model for their amplitudes of gust vane excitation across eight frequencies, at 25 ms^{-1}

A. Methodology

Testing was conducted in the 7ft by 5ft low-speed, closed-return wind tunnel at the University of Bristol. The model was mounted to a six-component overhead balance, which, with the aid of a rear strut, could vary the AoA of the model between -20 and 30 degrees.

The purpose of the testing was to compare the static and dynamic behaviour of six wing architectures: a locked wingtip with no external tank (referred to as the *Locked Baseline*), a free wingtip with no external tank (referred to as the *Free Baseline*), and then a locked or free wingtip with an external tank with either solid or liquid fuel mass. The external tanks could be mounted in one of three positions and, as illustrated in Tab. 1, there were seven possible filling levels. The key shown in Fig. 7 will be used to differentiate between each of these cases. For example, FL-3-150 denotes a free wingtip with the liquid external tank mounted in position three, with a filling level of 150 g.

The static performance of each wing architecture was measured across a range of flight conditions. At five wind speeds, equally spaced between 20 and 30 ms^{-1} , the AoA of the model was varied between zero and nine degrees in 1.5 degree increments, and at each point, a five-second sample was taken. This test was conducted for all combinations of tank positions and filling levels for the solid mass case, whereas a subset of the liquid cases were tested for comparison.

A dual-vane vertical gust generator [40], seen in Fig. 6, was utilised to measure the response of the six wing architectures to dynamic excitation. For each tank position and filling level, starting with the FS-X-X case, at each velocity tested, the AoA was set to ensure the fold angle of the wingtip was close to zero. The model was then exposed to a ‘family’ of 1MC gusts, which consisted of three different gust amplitudes at eight frequencies, which were evenly spaced between two and 15 Hz. The amplitude of the gust was defined by the maximum rotation of the gust vanes, and the relationship between the gust vane amplitude and the vertical velocity component experienced by the model can be seen in Fig. 8. Following this, the model was exposed to a quasi-random continuous turbulence sequence for 30 seconds, which was generated using the Von Kármán velocity spectra [41].

Next, the other five wing architectures were exposed to the same dynamic excitations, at the same velocities and AoAs, as the FS-X-X case. This both limited the test matrix to the likely cruise conditions and ensured the mean wing loading was similar for all architectures (with the exception of the free baseline case).

III. Numerical Modelling

To complement the experimental data, a low-fidelity numerical model was developed to explore the behaviour of a wing incorporating a floating fuel tank. The model, which is an adaptation of that presented in [19], consisted of a flexible, linear, inner wing and a rigid nonlinear wingtip, and the following sections outline the inclusion of the structural, aerodynamic and liquid sloshing models.

Table 2 Properties of the additional point masses distributed along the inner wing

Part Name	mass [g]	x [mm]	y [mm]	I_{xx} [kgmm ²]	I_{yy} [kgmm ²]
Inner Wing Panels	49	-19.1	[75,185,295]	38.9	45.6
Aileron Servo	11	-38.3	253	0	0
Inner Hinge Mass	47	-13.3	388	18.2	23.9

Table 3 Properties of the point masses used to derive the inertial properties of the wingtip, distances are expressed as the distance from the where the hinge line crosses the quarter-chord-line.

Part Name	mass [g]	x_t [mm]	y_t [mm]	z_t [mm]	I_{xx} [kgmm ²]	I_{yy} [kgmm ²]	I_{zz} [kgmm ²]
Wingtip	133	-18.4	69.4	0	530.0	82.0	607.1
200ml Solid Tank	52.8	-18.1	N/A	0	14.8	137.8	133.7
200ml Liquid Tank	41.0	-18.1	N/A	0	14.5	81.9	78.6
25g Mass	25.0	N/A	N/A	-27.5	1.0	1.0	1.7

A. Structural Model

The deformation of the inner wing was modelled using the Rayleigh Ritz assumed shapes method [42]. The vertical deformation of the flexural axis (z) and its rotation (η) are defined in the body reference frame[¶], and have the form

$$z(y, t) = \sum_{i=1}^N y^{i+1} q_i(t) \quad (2)$$

$$\eta(y, t) = \sum_{i=1}^M y^i q_{(N+i)}(t) \quad (3)$$

where q_i is the i^{th} generalised coordinate, b_i is the semi-span of the inner wing, and N and M are the number of bending and torsional shape functions respectively (which were chosen as $N = 3$ and $M = 2$). Likewise, the beam strain energy was modelled using Euler-Bernoulli beam theory, such that

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \left(\int_0^{b_b} EI \left(\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial y^2} \right)^2 dy + \int_0^{b_b} GJ \left(\frac{\partial \eta}{\partial y} \right)^2 dy \right) \quad (4)$$

where EI and GJ are the flexural rigidity and the torsional rigidity of the inner wing respectively, and b_b is the semi-span of the centre spar running along the quarter-chord-line of the model.

The mass of the beam section was modelled as a uniform mass distribution, and the secondary masses - such as 3D printed surfaces, servos and non-rotating hinge components - were modelled as point masses with associated moments of inertia, as outlined in Table 2. Therefore, the kinetic energy of the inner wing could be calculated as

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \left(\int_0^{b_i} \int_{-\frac{1}{2}w}^{\frac{1}{2}w} \rho d z^2 dx dy + \sum_{n=1}^N m_n \dot{z}(x_n, y_n)^2 + \sum_{n=1}^N I_{y_n} \dot{\eta}(x_n, y_n)^2 \right) \quad (5)$$

where w , d and ρ are the beam width, depth and density respectively, b_i is the semi-span of the inner wing, N is the number of additional point Masses, n is the n^{th} point mass as per the properties in table 2.

The wingtip was modelled as a rigid point mass connected to the tip of the inner wing via a hinge. Both the centre of mass and the inertial properties of the wingtip varied dependent on the location and mass of the external tank, with all relevant inertial properties shown in Tab. 3. The rotation matrix between the body and wingtip reference frame^{¶¶} can be defined as

$$A_{bf} = \mathbf{R}_x \left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial y}(b_i, t) \right) \mathbf{R}_y(\eta(b_i, t)) \mathbf{R}_z(\Lambda) \mathbf{R}_x(\theta) \mathbf{R}_z(-\Lambda) \quad (6)$$

[¶]in the body frame of reference, the x-axis points upstream along the fuselage, and the y axis is perpendicular to the XZ plane of symmetry of the aircraft and points out towards the starboard wingtip

^{¶¶}in the wingtip reference frame of the starboard wingtip, z is perpendicular to the wingtip and points down at a fold angle of zero degrees, y is parallel to the leading edge and points out towards the starboard wingtip, and x is perpendicular to the leading edge and points forwards

where Λ represents the flare angle, θ represents the fold angle and the operator $R_n(m)$ defines a 3D rotation matrix which describes an anti-clockwise rotation about the n^{th} axis by m radians. Therefore, the position of the wingtip point mass in the body reference is

$$\vec{p}_{ft} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ b_i \\ z(b_i, t) \end{bmatrix} + A_{bf} \begin{bmatrix} x_t \\ y_t \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

where x_t and y_t represent the displacement of the wingtips CoM from the flexural axis of the hinge. Therefore, the instantaneous rotational velocity in the body frame, ω , can be expressed as [43]

$$\hat{\omega} = A_{af}^T \dot{A}_{af} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\omega_z & \omega_y \\ \omega_z & 0 & -\omega_x \\ -\omega_y & \omega_x & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

where

$$\omega = [\omega_x \quad \omega_y \quad \omega_z]^T \quad (9)$$

leading to the following expression for the kinetic energy of the wingtip

$$T_t = \frac{1}{2} m_t \dot{\vec{p}}_t^T \dot{\vec{p}}_t + \frac{1}{2} \omega^T I \omega \quad (10)$$

where m_t is the mass of the wingtip and I is the wingtips moment of inertia tensor. The products of inertia are assumed to be zero, hence, I is a square, diagonal, matrix with the trace

$$\text{Trace}(I) = [I_{xx}, I_{yy}, I_{zz}] \quad (11)$$

where I_{xx} , I_{yy} and I_{zz} are the principle moments of inertia of the wingtip about its centre of mass as defined by the summation of relevant terms in Tab. 3. Using the derived equations for the kinetic and potential energy of each element, the equations of motion of the entire system were found using the Euler-Lagrange method - utilising the python packages moyra** and sympy [44] - and were of the form

$$M(\vec{q}, \dot{\vec{q}}) \ddot{\vec{q}} - f(\vec{q}, \dot{\vec{q}}) = 0 \quad (12)$$

where M is the generalised mass matrix and f is a matrix of additional forces.

B. Aerodynamic Forces

The aerodynamic forces acting on the wing were modelled using modified strip theory, in which both the inner wing and wingtip were discretised into 20 uniform strips. The aerodynamic force acting at the quarter-chord point of the i^{th} panel could then be estimated as

$$L_i = \frac{1}{2} \rho |\vec{V}_i| S_i a_i (\alpha_i + \alpha_0) \quad (13)$$

where \vec{V}_i is the local chordwise velocity vector, S_i is the planform area, a_i is the local lift-curve-slope, α_i is the local AoA, and α_0 accounts for wing camber. Both \vec{V}_i and α_i incorporate the induced velocity due to the motion of the wing. Therefore, for the inner wing the local chordwise velocity vector and AoA were defined as

$$\vec{V}_w = R_y(\alpha_r)^T \begin{bmatrix} u \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \dot{z} \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

$$\alpha_w = \arctan \left(\frac{\vec{V}_w \cdot \hat{n}}{\vec{V}_w \cdot \hat{i}} \right) \quad (15)$$

**<https://pypi.org/project/moyra/>[retrieved 08/12/2022]

where u is the wind speed, α_r is the root angle of attack, \hat{i} is the unit vector in the chordwise direction and \hat{n} is the unit vector normal to the strip. For the wingtip, the local chordwise velocity vector as

$$\vec{V}_f = (R_y(\alpha_r)A_{bf})^T \begin{bmatrix} u \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} - (A_{bf}^T \dot{\vec{p}}) \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

with the local AoA defined in a similar fashion to Eq. (15). To account for steady 3D effects, the local lift-curve-slope at each panel, a_i , was interpolated from the difference of two lift distributions that were pre-calculated using the vortex lattice method [45], at a fold angle of zero degrees.

To apply the aerodynamic forces back to the structure, the local force vector for each strip was converted into a generalised force using the principle of virtual work. This led to the final form of the equations of motion as

$$\mathbf{M}(\vec{q}, \dot{\vec{q}}) \ddot{\vec{q}} - \mathbf{f}(\vec{q}, \dot{\vec{q}}) = \mathbf{f}_a(\vec{q}, \dot{\vec{q}}) + \mathbf{f}_s(\vec{q}, \dot{\vec{q}}) \quad (17)$$

where $\mathbf{f}_a(\vec{q}, \dot{\vec{q}})$ represents a vector of external generalised aerodynamic forces, and $\mathbf{f}_s(\vec{q}, \dot{\vec{q}})$ represents a vector of generalised sloshing forces, which are derived in the next section.

C. Sloshing Reduced Order Model

Along with the aeroelastic system, a method is required to capture the hydrodynamic loading and induced damping effects that arise from internal liquid sloshing. To provide rapid simulation a low fidelity reduced-order sloshing model is employed which has particular advantages in capturing both small and large amplitude vertical excitation of fluid-filled tanks, such as the dynamic conditions arising in the floating wing tank. In particular, the chosen sloshing ROM is based upon the direct application of experimentally recorded sloshing forces, identified during prescribed harmonic vertical excitation of a rectangular tank [46, 47]. From these experiments, a map of the cycle-averaged sloshing forces across multiple excitation conditions can be constructed, allowing the kinematic excitation state to be linked with the instantaneous quasi-steady sloshing force. Following the inclusion of the relevant scaling laws, such data can be used to track the kinematic behaviour of the aeroelastic system and apply a representative sloshing force in response. This approach is formalised within Constantin et al.[36], where it was applied to the free-release of a scaled wing structure with multiple baffled fuel tanks, showing a good capability in resolving fluid-induced dissipation in complex systems. Further, a simplified version of this approach was previously applied in the aeroelastic setting in both pre- and post-critical flight conditions, and compared against a higher fidelity sloshing model [35].

A brief description of the sloshing ROM will be subsequently given focusing on its inclusion in the previously discussed aeroelastic framework, however, for a full description see [36]. Initially, considering the prescribed harmonic excitation of a structure with an internal partially-filled tank, at a set amplitude (A) and frequency (ω), where the vertical kinematics are

$$z = A \sin(\omega t), \quad \dot{z} = A\omega \cos(\omega t) \quad (18)$$

Throughout the cycles the total force (F_t) acting on the structure is measured and decomposed into the ‘‘sloshing force’’ (F_s) which is the result of having a dynamic medium (liquid) inside the tank. Averaging the sloshing force over multiple cycles allows for a ‘‘quasi-steady’’ (assuming the sloshing regime is fully developed) sloshing force (\bar{F}_s) to be recovered

$$F_s = F_t = (\ddot{z} - g)m_T \quad \Rightarrow \quad \bar{F}_s = g(z, \dot{z}, A, \omega) \sin(\omega t) \quad (19)$$

where m_T is the sum of structural and liquid masses undergoing excitation, noting that the sloshing force has no hydrostatic or inertial components included and is purely the result of dynamic liquid motion. The nonlinear function g is the basis of this ROM, and allows a mapping between kinematic excitation conditions and a representative hydrodynamic loading. From the experimental data, g is composed of a set of discrete points across a harmonic cycle evaluated over multiple amplitude and frequency conditions. For use in a numerical model, a continuous and smooth function for \bar{F}_s is required. To achieve this a radial-basis-function interpolation of the experimental data is performed resulting in the operator G , included in the aeroelastic model in the form

$$\bar{F}_s(\vec{q}, \dot{\vec{q}}, t) = m_l h_t \omega_c^2 G \left(\frac{\Delta z_{b,t}}{h_t}, \frac{\dot{z}_{b,t}}{\omega_c h_t}, \omega_c \right) S(t) \quad (20)$$

where m_l , h_t and ω_c are the liquid mass, internal tank height (assumed $h + r$) and the dominant frequency of excitation (i.e. first bending) used to provide the non-dimensional kinematics and sloshing forces interpolated in G and thus providing the hydrodynamic scaling between the data set and wing tank length scales. For clarity, an example of the operator G is given within Fig. 9, where a range of kinematic conditions have been interpolated for one discrete ω_c , forming a sloshing response surface [47]. Further, this ROM is purely one-dimensional in its nature, a result of the experimental data set, therefore the vertical tank motion in the body reference frame ($z_{b,t}, \dot{z}_{b,t}$) is extracted and used as the defining kinematics in the ROM. Noting that $\Delta z_{b,t}$ is the vertical displacement away from the trim condition and the kinematics are measured at the chord-centerline where the tank joins the wing (as listed in Table 3). $S(t)$ is a time-dependent smoothing function used to impose the transient fluid conditions following impulse excitation (such as a gust) onto the quasi-steady sloshing forces calculated in G which assumes the fluid is in a fully developed sloshing regime[36].

\bar{F}_s is computed and oriented in the global vertical direction. Using the principle of virtual work the generalised force $f_s(\vec{q}, \dot{\vec{q}})$ resulting from sloshing is formed completing Eqn. 17. As \bar{F}_s is devoid of hydrostatic or inertial components, the liquid inertia is lumped into the generalised mass matrix within the aeroelastic model. The state-space model of the coupled aeroelastic-sloshing framework is time integrated in Matlab using the Runge-Kutta 45 pair implemented within the ODE45 solver [48]. A series of aerodynamic excitation states are applied to the model, including one-minus-cosine gusts and continuous turbulence. To ensure consistency with the experimental data the free-stream perturbations following the excitation are recorded with a series of pitot tubes measuring all three velocity components, which are fed directly into the numerical model.

Fig. 9 A response surface generated from the ROM interpolation at $\omega_c = 6.3$ Hz

IV. Results

A. Static Aeroelastic Behaviour

Figures 10 and 11 show how the lift, lift-to-drag ratio, and fold angle, of four wing layouts varied with AoA, at 22.5 ms^{-1} and 30 ms^{-1} respectively. At both velocities the “locked baseline” configuration (no external tank) had the best overall lift-to-drag ratio, peaking at an AoA of approximately six degrees at both velocities. The “Free Baseline” configuration indicates that when the wingtip is released the fold angle typically increases, and this increase grows with increasing AoA. This change in fold angle unloads the wingtip, reducing the total lift produced by the wing (see Fig. 10). This reduction in wingtip lift is beneficial in the context of FFWT load alleviation, as even when the AoA is corrected to maintain the same total lift, the centre of pressure of the wing will move inboard, reducing wing root bending loads. However, this reduction in lift changes the overall wing shape, moving it away from the designed optima, and reducing the maximum lift-to-drag ratio.

Regarding external fuel tanks, Fig. 10 shows that both the dry locked (LS-3-75), and the “Locked Baseline” configurations produce comparable quantities of lift. However, due to the increase in both the frontal and wetted area of the external tank, there is increased drag in the LS-3-75 configuration, reducing its peak lift-to-drag ratio. Albeit, if the fuel were stored within the wingtip structure, there would be no apparent increase in drag. When the wingtip is released (FS-3-75), Fig. 10 shows that the increased mass of the wingtip reduces its fold angle when compared to the “Free Baseline” configuration, and at an AoA of 6.4 deg the fold angle is approximately zero. At this AoA, which is highlighted by the grey dashed line in Fig. 10, both the total lift produced by the wing and the lift-to-drag ratio, are similar to that of the dry locked configuration.

At larger dynamic pressures the wingtip produces more lift at a given fold angle, therefore, its equilibrium fold angle must increase to balance the moments about the hinge. This is highlighted in Fig. 11, in which the AoA at which the fold angle is zero has reduced to 3 degrees. Equally the point at which the lift and lift-to-drag ratio of the locked and free configurations is comparable has also reduced to 3 degrees. These results suggest that when a wingtip coasts at a fold angle equal to the intended design angle, the steady aerodynamic performance of the wing is equivalent to the locked configuration.

During cruise, both the trim AoA and fuel load of an aircraft reduce with time. Figure 12 shows how the optimal AoA (the AoA at which the wingtip is at a fold angle of zero) varies with filling level and velocity. It shows that reducing the filling level reduces the optimal AoA, as less lift is required to balance the moments about the hinge. Furthermore, Fig. 14 shows that the possible range of optimal AoAs reduces with increasing dynamic pressure, as a smaller change in fold angle is required to get the same change in the lift on the wingtip. To rephrase these findings, if it was possible to alter the filling level of the tank during flight, and the cruise speed of the wind tunnel model was, for example, 25 ms^{-1} , the possible range of trim AoAs during flight would need to be between 3 to 6.5 deg to ensure the optimal lift-to-drag ratio of the aircraft could be maintained.

Figure 13 shows the variation in the optimal AoA when the external tanks were moved between positions 1, 2 and 3 on the wingtip (shown in Fig. 3). As the equilibrium position of an FFWT is defined by the balance of aerodynamic and gravitational moments about the hinge, a tank mounted closer to the hinge can carry more mass at a given AoA to achieve the same fold angle. Therefore, when sizing such a system for an aircraft, there will likely be a trade-off between maximum fuel mass, cruise performance, and other parameters such as changes in the dynamic behaviour.

Lastly in this section, only small differences were found between the equilibrium positions of the wet and dry configurations (Fig. 14). The small variations seen in Fig. 14 were thought to be due to the movement of the centre of mass of the liquid at different AoAs – albeit no definitive trend could be found to support this hypothesis, indicating that the effect is minor in comparison to systematic errors, such as the mass in each configuration.

Fig. 10 Variation in the Lift, Lift-to-Drag ratio, fold angle, and wing root bending moment with AoA, for four wing layouts, at a wind speed of 22.5 ms⁻¹

Fig. 11 Variation in the Lift, Lift-to-Drag ratio, fold angle, and wing root bending moment with AoA, for four wing layouts, at a wind speed of 30 ms⁻¹

Fig. 12 Variation in the AoA at which the fold angle of the wingtip is zero, for different solid tank filling levels and tunnel wind speeds.

Fig. 13 Variation in the AoA at which the fold angle of the wingtip is zero, for different solid tank positions (at 75 g filling level) and tunnel wind speeds.

Fig. 14 variation in the fold angle of the wingtip for different filling levels with both liquid and solid mass, at a wind speed of 27.5 ms^{-1}

B. Response of One-Minus-Cosine Gust Encounters

In regards to gust load alleviation, Castrichini et al. [8] showed that FFWTs provide two primary benefits. Firstly, releasing the wingtips reduces the mean wing loading – reducing the steady-state wing root bending moment (WRBM). Secondly, the dynamic response of an FFWT during one-minus-cosine gust encounters reduces the incremental WRBM experienced by the wing, when compared to hinge locked configuration. Figure 15a shows the experimental variation in the WRBM of the baseline locked and free configurations during a one-minus-cosine gust encounter, it shows that the combination of these two primary effects can lead to significant reductions in WRBM (29% in this example). However, it must be noted that because both configurations are at the same AoA, the free case produces less total lift. Typically in flight the AoA of the aircraft would change to maintain the same total lift, therefore, by scaling the lift of the free case to match that of the locked case, and by scaling the WRBM by the same factor, a more representative reduction in mean WRBM can be estimated. Assuming the response of the system is linear about the equilibrium position the incremental WRBM should be independent of the total wing loading, therefore the incremental WRBM is not scaled by this factor. Overall, this correction factor reduces the reduction in peak WRBM to 17% in the example shown in Fig. 15a.

Figure 16 shows how both the corrected absolute and incremental minimum and maximum WRBM vary with frequency for the free and locked baseline configurations. It should be noted, that in Fig. 16b the values were normalised using the incremental vertical gust components shown in Fig. 8, therefore, the values in Fig. 16 represent the effective incremental WRBM to a unit vertical one-minus-cosine gust encounter. In Fig. 8, the maximum incremental WRBM of the free configuration is less than that of the locked configuration, reaffirming the secondary benefit of FFWTs. However, Fig.16 also shows that the absolute minimum incremental WRBM is larger for the free configuration, although this is typically less of a concern in the sizing of aircraft.

Following the baseline configuration, IMC excitation tests were conducted with the floating wing tank. As shown in Fig. 12 multiple filling levels were tested, however, within the following sections only the 75 g (45% filling level) case is presented. It was observed in the experimental campaign that this filling level generally maximised the sloshing response, noting roughly 50% filling level is known to maximise fluid-induced dissipation [49]. Therefore, this case is presented within the subsequent sections where the focus lies on the sloshing response. Regarding the case of a solid external fuel tank, in the locked configuration, due to the weight of the tank, there should be a small reduction in mean WRBM. For the LS-3-75 case this reduction in WRBM should equal $\approx 0.6\text{Nm}$, however, experimentally an inertial relief of 0.4Nm was recorded. The reason for this difference is currently unknown but is likely either due to the effect of the external tank on aerodynamic forces, or systematic errors in comparing absolute WRBMs across multiple days of testing.

Regarding the free configuration, as is detailed in section II.A, all experimental dynamic responses were conducted close to a fold angle of zero degrees, therefore, there will be little change in the mean WRBM between the locked and free configurations. Figure 15b highlights this point, and also indicates that for this particular gust case, the incremental WRBM is larger for the free configuration. This is re-affirmed in Fig. 16, in which at high frequencies the incremental WRBM is higher for the free external tank when compared to the locked case. However, at lower frequencies, the

Fig. 15 Example experimental responses to a one-minus-cosine gust encounter.

incremental WRBM for the locked case is higher, and the maximum overall WRBM is also higher in the locked external tank configuration.

Comparing FS-3-75 to the free baseline configuration in Fig. 16, both follow similar trends with good load alleviation seen at lower frequencies when compared to the baseline locked configuration, however, overall the free baseline configuration has a reduced peak incremental WRBM across all frequencies.

Figure 17a shows that as the filling level of the solid tank is increased the incremental WRBM of the locked configuration reduces at higher frequencies, albeit there is a much smaller reduction in the overall maximum WRBM, which occurs at a frequency of 3.5 Hz. Furthermore, Fig. 17b indicates that the response of the free configuration shows little variation with the filling level.

Figure 18 shows that the position of the tank has a significant impact on the incremental WRBM of both the locked and free configurations. In the Locked configuration, Fig. 18a shows that moving the tank inboard increases the incremental WRBM at higher frequencies. This may be due to variations in modal frequencies; the movement of the mass inboard reduces the modal mass of both the wingtip mode and the first bending mode. This increases the frequency of both modes, meaning that they are more responsive to higher-frequency gusts - increasing the incremental WRBM seen during gust encounters.

Regarding the free configuration, moving the tank inboard reduces the maximum incremental WRBM by up to 22% (Fig. 18b). The mechanism for this reduction is under investigation, but when compared with Fig. 17b suggests the location of the centre of mass, rather than the total moment of inertia about the hinge, has a significant impact on the gust load alleviation of FFWTs. It is important to state here that the FS-1-75 case has a 9% smaller maximum incremental WRBM than the “free baseline” configuration, albeit with a larger mean WRBM.

In the context of FFWTs enabling longer wingspans by reducing WRBM, table 4 shows the maximum reduction in both absolute and incremental WRBM for the four configurations in Fig. 16 as well as FS-1-75. When considering incremental WRBM alone the FS-1-75 configuration has the best maximum reduction in WRBM of 35%. However, once values are corrected for variations in the total lift, the absolute reduction in peak WRBM for the free configuration marginally outperforms FS-1-75 with a 22% reduction compared to the 21% of FS-1-75. These results both highlight the importance of the reduction in mean WRBM provided by a lighter wingtip, but also suggest that, with careful consideration of the mass distribution of the wingtip, similar load alleviation can be achieved when using a wingtip equipped with an external fuel tank.

Fig. 16 Variation in the corrected a) absolute and b) incremental, WRBM for four wingtip configurations across a range of gust frequencies.

Table 4 Variation in the corrected incremental and absolute WRBM when compared to the baseline locked configuration.

Configuration	Corrected Mean WRBM [Nm]	Max. Inc. WRBM [Nm]	Max. WRBM [Nm]	% var. Inc from Baseline	% var. Total from Baseline
Baseline Locked	3.09	3.19	6.28	0.0	0.0
LS-3-75	2.74	2.97	5.71	6.9	8.62
FS-3-75	2.91	2.66	5.57	16.6	3.2
FS-1-75	2.88	2.07	4.95	35.1	21.2
Free	2.63	2.27	4.90	28.8	22.0
Free uncorrected	1.84	2.27	4.11	28.8	34.6

Fig. 17 Variation in the corrected incremental WRBM across a range of gust frequencies, for three tank filling levels, in both the locked and free configuration

Fig. 18 Variation in the corrected incremental WRBM across a range of gust frequencies, for three tank locations, in both the locked and free configuration

C. The Effect of Liquid Sloshing

Figure 19 shows both the numerical and experimental response of the locked wing configuration to two amplitudes of one-minus-cosine gust for both the liquid and solid external tank cases. Figure 19a shows that at a gust vane amplitude of 10 degrees there is little difference between the response of the two configurations; there is a small variation in the frequency of the system, this is likely due to the small variations in the total mass or mass distribution from the internal liquid shifting, but it is also indicative of dynamic fluid motion. Excitation of free-surface waves results in partially floating fluid that is inertially absent from the aeroelastic system, potentially inducing the observed stiffening behaviour. However, the magnitude of the first positive and negative peaks are similar, which are the primary metrics of gust loading. At a gust vane amplitude of 15 degrees, Fig. 19b shows that the response of the liquid case has dramatically changed, with a large increase in damping occurring between half a cycle and 3 cycles, with a reduction in the rate of damping beyond the 3rd cycle. This result is indicative of the onset of violent internal sloshing [49], significant energy input from the structure excites free surface motion, requiring a series of cycles to develop due to inertial effects. Upon development of the violent sloshing regime, fluid-structure impacts that have a delayed phase result in significant net energy dissipation from the exciting structure.

However, as the reduction in damping does not occur over the first half cycle, the liquid has little effect on the amplitude of the first positive peak, and only slightly reduces the magnitude of the first negative peak – the key metrics when measuring gust loading. Figure 20b shows that this conclusion is repeated across all gust frequencies, with the only significant impact of liquid on the incremental WRBM envelope being to reduce the magnitude of the negative peak. Additionally, Fig. 20a shows that this effect is most apparent in the outboard-most tank position, which likely has the largest amplitude of oscillation during a one-minus-cosine gust encounter.

Figure 21 shows the experimental and numerical response of the free wingtip, at two tank positions, to a one-minus-cosine gust for both liquid and solid external tank configurations. Figure 21b shows that in tank position 3, there is no variation in the response of the liquid and solid mass cases and that when the tank is moved inboard the effect of liquid sloshing begins to have a small impact in the response of the system (see Fig. 21a). The reduced influence of sloshing dynamics in the free configuration was initially surprising, as during these gust encounters fold angles of greater than ± 10 degrees were achieved.

Figure 22 shows the shape of the first bending mode at a velocity of 27.5 ms^{-1} , for the three tank positions. At tank positions two and three the large point mass of the external tank acts as a node, meaning that the external tank exhibits little motion and the wingtip rotates about it, explaining the reduced impact of sloshing dynamics seen in Fig. 21b. At tank position one, the external tank is too close to the hinge to act as a node, and therefore, will exhibit more vertical motion during gust encounters, leading to the small influence of sloshing dynamics seen in Fig. 21a.

These features are also observed in the numerical model, again for the third tank position little numerical dissipation is produced due to the reduced tank heave displacements. However, considering the first tank position no dissipation is captured in the model, unlike the experimental case which exhibits a light additional fluid damping. Noting the mode shapes in Fig. 22 large rotational and spanwise dynamics of the tank can be expected, which are not accounted for in the single degree of freedom (heave) sloshing ROM.

Fig. 19 Example experimental and numerical responses to a one-minus-cosine gust encounter, with both liquid and solid fuel mass.

Fig. 20 Experimental variation in the corrected incremental WRBM across a range of gust frequencies, for two tank locations, in both the locked and free configuration with liquid and solid fuel mass.

Fig. 21 Example experimental and numerical responses to a one-minus-cosine gust encounter of amplitude 15 deg, for both liquid and solid fuel mass.

Fig. 22 Variation in the mode shape of the first bending mode at a wind speed of 27.5 ms^{-1} , at three tank positions

D. Response to Random Turbulence

The response of a wing to a random turbulence encounter may be compared by looking at the root mean square (RMS) of the incremental WRBM during a turbulence encounter. Comparing the response of the locked and free baseline configurations in Figure 23a, it is first important to notice the reduction in mean WRBM due to the release of the wingtip. Although the RMS WRBM is 35% higher in the free wingtip configuration (see Fig. 23b) the absolute loading on the wing is comparable. This increase in RMS of a free wingtip relative to a locked wingtip is true in the case of a floating fuel tank as well, with little variation in RMS seen across all three free configurations (see Fig. 23). However, as the mean WRBM of the floating fuel tank is comparable to the locked case, the floating fuel tanks exhibit the largest absolute WRBM.

Regarding locked fuel tank configurations, the RMS WRBM shown in Fig. 23 is lower than that of the baseline locked configuration. Additionally, there is a 12% reduction in the RMS between the solid and liquid-locked cases, suggesting that liquid sloshing may reduce the loading experienced by the wing during a random turbulence encounter. This finding is corroborated by the numerical simulation, shown in Fig. 23, which indicates a 13% decrease in the RMS between the liquid and solid locked configurations. Increasing the filling level is shown to reduce this effect, with Fig. 24 showing no reduction in the RMS due to liquid motion within the 150 g fuel mass case. This increase in the influence of sloshing with a reduction in filling level can be understood by considering that a lighter wing will respond more to gust encounters, increasing the motion of the fluid. This effect will peak at some filling level [49], as at zero filling level the solid and liquid configurations must have identical responses, however, the location of this peak is not observed within this dataset.

Figure 25 shows how both the experimental and numerical RMS varies with tank position, with a good correlation seen across both datasets. As the tank moves inboard the RMS in the locked configuration increases slightly, and the RMS of the free configuration reduces, tending towards that of the locked case – as if the tank was placed at the hinge the two responses would be identical. Furthermore, as the tank position moves inboard some sloshing effects begin to emerge, due to the increased relative motion of the tank, as alluded to in Fig. 22.

Overall, these results show that releasing an FFWT increases the incremental WRBM RMS due to turbulence encounters. In configurations with a light wingtip, this effect is mitigated by the reduction in mean WRBM due to the unloading of the wingtip. However, in the case of a floating fuel tank, this increase in RMS increases the absolute loads experienced by the wing, and may become a limiting factor in the sizing process of such an aircraft, although this effect can be mitigated with careful consideration of the mass distribution of the wingtip.

Fig. 23 Variation in the mean WRBM and the RMS WRBM during a turbulence encounter for both the numerical and experimental models. a) bars represent mean WRBM and error bars the RMS b) bars represent the RMS. Wind speed 27.5 ms^{-1}

Fig. 24 Experimental variation in the RMS WRBM during a random turbulence encounter, at multiple filling levels

Fig. 25 Experimental and numerical variation the RMS WRBM during a random turbulence encounter, in both the locked and free configuration with liquid and solid fuel mass.

V. Conclusion

This paper presents a novel wind tunnel experiment into the static and dynamic behaviour of a ‘floating wingtip fuel tank’. This device consists of a ‘freely floating’ wingtip with an additional mass attached, in the form of a fuel tank, to ensure an optimal lift distribution during cruise, whilst also acting as a passive load alleviation device, that would not need to be actively released during operation. By altering the fuel tank filling level, it is shown that the wingtip can float at an optimal angle for aerodynamic efficiency across a range of angles of attack (AoAs). Furthermore, by altering the position of the fuel tank it is shown that the maximum fuel load can be increased whilst maintaining the optimal equilibrium angle of the wingtip. Regarding gust load alleviation, the response of a floating fuel tank to both one-minus-cosine gust encounters and a random turbulence sequence is presented, and it was shown that, through the careful selection of the centre of mass of the wingtip, load alleviation comparable to that of a wingtip without a fuel tank can be achieved. Additionally, a comparison is made between liquid and solid mass, and it is shown that the motion of the fluid can reduce loading during random turbulence, whilst having a negligible effect on one-minus-cosine gust encounters. Such results are also confirmed by a numerical model incorporating aeroelastic and sloshing models. The simple fluid reduced order model provides a good representation of the complex internal hydrodynamics, capturing the induced dissipation following large vertical tank motions, but has reduced capability when rotational and spanwise tank motions are dominant. Overall, the floating wingtip fuel tank is shown to be a viable concept, which could enable longer wingspans whilst increasing the fuel capacity of an aircraft. It is recommended that future work on such a concept focus on the device’s effect on manoeuvre loads as well as the effect of the rigid body motion of the aircraft during gust encounters.

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